

مفهوم و روش‌های اندازه‌گیری هم‌دینی
در مطالعات اقتضایی مدیریت

علینقی مشایخی*، محمد ابویی اردکان

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چکیده

واژه‌های کلیدی:

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دسته‌بندی «جويس، اسلو کام، و گلینو»

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الف) هم‌دیفی تأثیری:

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1. Blocking
 2. Substitute

دسته بندی «ون دِ ون و درازین»^۱

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الف) رویکرد انتخابی

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1. Van de Ven & Drazin
 2. Axiom
 3. Perrow

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ب) رویکرد تعاملی

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ث) رویکرد سیستمی

1. Bateson
2. Error of logical typing
3. Whole
4. Reductionism

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1. Pattern Analysis
2. Equifinality

ج. ١. تحليل الكو

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$$DIST_{ij} = \sqrt{\sum_{s=1}^N (X_{is} - X_{js})^2}$$

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$$= X_{is}$$

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ج. ۲. هم پایانی

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دسته بندی و نکات امان

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1. Trade-off
 2. Child

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	(Gestalts)	(Profile Deviation)	
	(Covariation)	(Mediation)	
	(Matching)	(Moderation)	

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الف) همردیفی به عنوان تعدیل کنندگی

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ج) همردیفی به عنوان جور کردن

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1. Hambrick
 2. Prescott
 3. Chandler

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د) همردیفی به عنوان انحراف از پروفایل

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X_c

X_s

مقیاس استاندارد شده برای اندازه گیری ابعاد				اهمیت	ابعاد راهبرد
+1		0	-1		
	X_{c1}		X_{s1}	b_1	X_1
				b_2	X_2
				b_3	X_3
				b_4	X_4
				b_5	X_5
	X_{s6}		X_{c6}	b_6	X_6

هـ) همردیفی به عنوان گشتالت

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و) همردیفی به عنوان هم تغییری

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نتیجه گیری

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ACADEMY OF MANAGEMENT REVIEW

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	(Gestalts)	/(Systems) (Equifinality)	—	(Profile Deviation)	/(Systems) (Pattern Analysis)	—
	(Covariation)			(Mediation)		(Functional- Blocking Effect)
	(Matching)	(Selection)	(General) (Effect)	(Moderation)	(Interaction)	— (Functional- Substitute Effect)

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